

Agro2Circular

D8.2 – Interim Report on Dissemination and Communication

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Technical references

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* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Summary

The aim of this document is to give account of the Communication and Dissemination activities implemented within the first 18 months of implementation of the Agro2Circular project, covering from M1 (October 2021) until M18 (March 2023). These activities have been rolled out in the framework of the “Dissemination and Communication Strategy” (D8.1), which lays down the overarching strategy and workplan to disseminate and communicate Agro2Circular activities and results, following a multi-actor and multi-channel approach to generate wider stakeholders’ engagement.

The current report will undergo a final release towards the end of the project (D8.3).

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Item	Description
A2C	Agro2Circular
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CEI	Community Engagement Index
CED	Communication Engagement Dissemination

1. Communication and Dissemination strategy

The Agro2Circular Communication, Engagement and Dissemination strategy is formed by complementary approaches and activities:

- Communication aims at raising visibility and awareness of project activities, goals, results, impacts and benefits, addressing non-technical audiences and the general public. This is done by conveying laymen and easy-to-understand contents and messages. Communication provides a first, necessary step to generate wide social acceptance of the proposed Agro2Circular innovation related to recycling and upcycling of agri-food sector residues.
- Engagement aims to create a solid and two-way connection with the selected stakeholders, facilitating their proactive involvement in Agro2Circular's activities to ensure that their views, needs and expectations are always considered and integrated into the development process of Agro2Circular's solutions.
- Dissemination aims at raising acceptance and uptake of Agro2Circular's results, enabling smooth transfer of knowledge, skills and data for technical audiences across the agri-food value chains. Dissemination measures are necessary to build a wide and community at EU, local and regional level around Agro2Circular.

The Communication and Dissemination strategy of Agro2Circular is highly integrated with the goals of the Exploitation activities, fostering the uptake and sustainability of its results beyond the project end.

The CED strategy is deployed at both European/international level and local/regional/national level. At EU/international level, ICONS (in collaboration with CETEC as project coordinator) is in charge to lead the official project C&D activities and the external relations towards European/international stakeholders, supporting the partners' individual activities and facilitating the smooth implementation of the C&D Plan. At local/regional/national level, local partners (PRIMA, KVC, AGROFOOD) are the main touchpoint of the project towards local stakeholders and communities.

Throughout the implementation of Agro2Circular, a continuous monitoring exercise is carried out to assess the impacts generated by the project's C&D activities. The monitoring and impact assessment activities provide feedback for future fine-tuning of the C&D strategy, hence boosting the effectiveness of the overall C&D effort.

Progress of Communication & Dissemination tools

Multiple C&D channels and tools are leveraged to reach out to different target audiences and meet their needs and expectations. The variety of channels and tools is meant to increase the coverage and effectiveness of the whole C&D campaign, maximising the impacts created by Agro2Circular throughout its different phases of implementation. An overview of the progress for the implementation of all the scheduled C&D tools for Agro2Circular is provided with the table below:

Table 1 Progress of C&D activities implementation

	Industry / SMEs	Associations (agri-food, industrial)	Policy Makers	Research communities / Academia	General public	KPI	Progress
Leaflet / Postcard	Completed	Completed	Completed	Completed	Completed	1	1 – Achieved
Roll-up	Completed	Completed	Completed	Completed	Completed	1	1 – Achieved
Newsletter	Ongoing	Ongoing		Ongoing	Ongoing	6	1 - ongoing
Presentation video	Completed	Completed	Completed	Completed	Completed	1	1 – Achieved
Video interviews	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	NA	2 - ongoing
Journalistic articles and interviews	Upcoming	Upcoming		Upcoming	Upcoming	2	Upcoming
Press and News releases	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	Ongoing	20	14
Final video	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	1	Upcoming

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101036838.

Scientific publications, posters, oral presentations and articles in industrial magazines	8	9	4	5	7	30	32 oral presentations 3 posters
Lectures/Workshops fostering public engagement	Upcoming	Upcoming			Ongoing	20	4 lectures in schools
Info-packs	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	3	Upcoming
Best practice Book	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming	Upcoming		1	Upcoming
Deliverables' abstract	Upcoming	Upcoming		Upcoming		8	Upcoming

2. Communication and Dissemination tools

Visual Identity

The visual identity of Agro2Circular is a consistent graphic system designed to make the project outputs stand out and be easily recognizable from external audiences. The visual identity includes the main project logo (reflecting Agro2Circular's concept and core values), the logo variants for different use contexts and graphic elements (colour codes and palette, typography, fonts). The full visual identity is based on the results of a *brand personality* exercise conducted by ICONS, with the collaboration of CETEC as project coordinator. The exercise was aimed at catching and analysing the key features, mission and vision of Agro2Circular, to be then translated into graphic traits suitable to convey the project messages. The full visual identity is described in the project brandbook, is available at the following link:

https://agro2circular.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/A2C_Brandbook.pdf .

Figure 1 A2C Logo (Main)

Color Palette

Primary

Secondary

Figure 2 A2C Colour scheme

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

Table 2 Visual identity and logo main info

Accountability	The Agro2Circular logo and visual identity have been developed by ICONS
Input	CETEC provided feedback and inputs along the design process, participating to the brand personality exercise.
Timing / Deviations	The brandbook, describing the full visual identity, has been released at M3. No deviations occurred.
Task / Deliverable	Task 8.2 “Visual Identity”
Next steps	NA
Link	Brandbook available as Annex I of this document

Postcard, Leaflet and roll-up

The project postcard, leaflet and roll-up are communication supporting materials aimed at raising project visibility and sharing its core objective with a broad audience, on the occasion of both face-to-face and virtual events. The postcard includes a short text description of the Agro2Circular project and a QR code redirecting to the project website (www.Agro2Circularproject.eu), always providing direct access to the latest project updates. The leaflet, instead, is a more complex communication format designed to provide more detailed information about the project. Both materials have been designed both in English and in Spanish, to boost local distribution at the demo case in Spain.

Figure 3 A2C Postcard

The wheel of change

A2C is a EU project proposing innovative valorisation routes for agri-food wastes upcycling and circular economy development through:

- High extraction yields
- Pure and stable bioactives for new food production
- Cosmetic and nutraceutical formulation
- Recyclable multilayer plastic
- Digital platform for product tracing and market prediction

Circularity is the answer

- Reducing the consumption of primary materials (fossil, biomass and metal ores) in >13,000 tonnes
- Improve sustainability and circularity of clusters' economic sectors, natural ecosystems, management and valorisation of local resources
 - Decreasing >27,000 tonnes CO2 eq emissions
 - 15 new key exploitable results and >30 new circular business models, generating a turnover of 166.8M€
 - Job creation: short term (26) -> medium term (295) -> through replication (590-2655)
 - >30 business ideas and establishment of >100 local alliances

Radial point turning the tide

Agro2Circular proposes scalable territorial systemic solutions that are:

**Sustainable
Regenerative
Inclusive
Fair**

A reinvented wheel to boost urban®ional economies while empowering all involved actors (citizens, industries, decision makers, academia) and fostering good practices.

Let it spin!

A circular shape for a perfect spin

Spin the wheel, change the future

La reinención de la rueda

40% de los residuos se reutilizan

En el contexto agroalimentario actual:

- La cadena de valor no es sostenible
- El sector hortofrutícola produce el 40% de los residuos alimentarios
- Los filmes de plástico multicapa utilizados en la agricultura y el envasado acaban en vertederos (34%) o se incineran (66%)
- No existen soluciones integrales para la implantación territorial de la economía circular

¿Que beneficio tiene una rueda que no gira?

Únete a la revolución: ¡ponte en contacto!

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agro2circular.eu/es @Agro2Circular

Una nueva rueda en cuatro pasos:
Reciclar los residuos agroalimentarios
Reciclar el plástico multicapa
Asegurar la trazabilidad de los residuos
Replicar el modelo en otros territorios

Este proyecto ha recibido financiación del programa de investigación e innovación Horizonte 2020 de la Unión Europea en virtud del acuerdo de subvención nº 101036838

El valor oculto de los residuos del sector agroalimentario

Figure 4 A2C Leaflet

The roll-up is a self-supporting advertising banner, aimed to display the basic project information and catch the attention of the audience during face-to-face events.

Presentation video

The project presentation video offers a concise and visually appealing overview of Agro2Circular's rationale and goals, facilitating a first contact between different audiences and the project ecosystem. The video has been developed using a unique graphic technique called “stop-motion”, being the most suitable one enabling to valorise and strengthen the A2C project's identity while catching attention from a broader audience and generate interest on professional target groups, pushing them to get to know more about the project.

The video is available at the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6tLaAdQXcRs>

Figure 5 A2C video overview

Table 3 Presentation video main info

Accountability	The Agro2Circular presentation video has been developed by ICONS.
Input	CETEC provided key support in the definition of the concept and script of the video.
Timing / Deviations	The Agro2Circular presentation video has been released at M10. No deviation.
Task / Deliverable	Task 8.2 “Visual Identity”
Next steps	NA
Link	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6tLaAdQXcRs

Journalistic articles, Press & News Releases

Journalistic articles, press and news releases are editorial formats adopted by Agro2Circular to keep the wide audience informed on the main activities of the project, while delving into its main aspects and challenges. Press releases are used to make formal announcements of project milestones and achievements, shared with media outlets for wide public outreach. News releases, on the other hand, have an informal structure of blog posts and are meant to share scientific explanation, interesting background stories or events and initiatives relevant with the Agro2Circular ecosystem. Lastly, journalistic articles are editorial formats aiming to capture the attention of the media and the general public on a newsworthy story derived from the innovative aspects of the project. Until M18, Agro2Circular has released 1 press release and 12 news releases. Once published on the project website, journalistic articles, press and news releases have been distributed across the alphagalileo.org and phys.org media multipliers. Moreover, the journalistic articles will be also released on youris.com, a major public communication portal on EU research and innovation directly managed by ICONS.

Table 4 Editorial formats for communication main info

Accountability	ICONS is in charge for the development and distribution of these editorial formats.
Input	All project partners contribute with technical contents, input and statements for the articles.
Timing / Deviations	Ongoing
Task / Deliverable	Task 8.4 “Outreach at European Level”
Next steps	Releases of journalistic articles, press and news releases to be developed following the project progress.

Link	News Page (English): https://agro2circular.eu/news-events/ News Page (Spanish): https://agro2circular.eu/es/noticias-y-eventos/
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Newsletter

A project e-newsletter is sent out to the subscribers of the Agro2Circular website, with the goal to directly share periodic updates on the Agro2Circular activities and progress, while promoting specific events and initiatives. A dedicated subscription form is available on the project website. The newsletters reach out to the Agro2Circular professional community and the general public, to keep them informed of the progress made by the project. Moreover, it has been used to promote relevant events and activities, sharing useful and practical information for the community. The e-newsletter is written in English, developed and distributed with a dedicated Wordpress plugin, built-in into the website's back-end. All the issues delivered are also available on the "News" section of the Agro2Circular website.

Figure 6 A2C Newsletter overview

Table 5 Newsletter main info

Accountability	ICONS is in charge for the development and distribution of the newsletter
Input	All project partners contribute with statements, news items to be promoted and help with the distribution, advertising the newsletter with their own communities.
Timing / Deviations	Ongoing. Newsletter #1 has been issued on September 2022
Task / Deliverable	Task 8.4 "Outreach at European Level"
Next steps	Newsletter #2 expected to be released by May 2023.
Link	Newsletter #1: https://agro2circular.eu/?na=v&nk=52-50fc45512d&id=1

3. Online channels for Communication and Dissemination

Website

The website is the main online communication channel for the project, and the first interface tools for many Agro2Circular different audiences. The main aim of the website is to increase stakeholders' awareness, acceptance, uptake on Agro2Circular project and to attract the attention of potential stakeholders.

The website contents are accessible to the viewers with no restrictions.

A temporary landing page was released in December 2021 to provide all the necessary information about Agro2Circular before the release of the website.

Figure 7 A2C Landing Page

The landing page was replaced by the website in February 2022 (M4). To avoid losing audience, the landing page and the website share the same URL: <https://agro2circular.eu>. Agro2Circular website is a flexible tool, designed to adapt to the different needs of the project during all its life stages. It is constantly updated with the project's news and events, it has a section dedicated to project's internal and resources (such as public deliverables). It has

been developed both in English and in Spanish language to address both international and local audiences at the Spanish demo.

Figure 8 A2C Spanish homepage

New sections will be added in time according to the project's needs.

Registered users' contact details will be treated as fully confidential, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). ICONS will act as the Data Controller to ensure that the sensitive information of the stakeholders and users registered in the online platform/website will remain strictly confidential. Followers' contact details are used uniquely for the dissemination of Agro2Circular project and no other purpose. Users are granted the right to access the information they provided upon online registration and to decide to opt out from the project contact list at any time.

Figure 9 Website homepage overview

Table 6 Website main info

Accountability	Both Agro2Circular landing page and website are developed and maintained by ICONS, with input and feedback from CETEC. <i>In compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), private data will remain confidential as ICONS will act as the Data Controller and be responsible for treating all the sensitive data provided by the registered users upon online registration.</i>
Input	All partners participate by sending inputs for news, events, and scientific papers. ICONS actively research news, events, and journalistic articles topics.
Timing/ deviation	The landing page was released on December 2021 The project website was released on February 2022 No deviation
Task/deliverable	Task 8.2 “Project Identity and Online Channels”
Link	https://agro2circular.eu

Social Media

The management of Agro2Circular website is backed up by a comprehensive social media strategy that aims to maximise the project's outreach.

Agro2Circular has two social media channels: LinkedIn and Twitter, managed by ICONS. These accounts are supported by the consortium partners social media account to be exploited to expand Agro2Circular stakeholder's network, starting from the project's already partners' existing stakeholders' communities.

Figure 10 A2C Social media channels

Table 7 Social media accounts and followers

Account	Social media	Followers
https://twitter.com/Agro2Circular	Twitter	418
https://www.linkedin.com/company/agro2circular/?viewAsMember=true	LinkedIn	213

An official hashtag has been set (**#Agro2Circular**) to track the impact of the social media conversation about the project. The hashtag was presented during the project kick-off meeting and all partners are invited to use it. This hashtag will be used to monitor posts about Agro2Circular, to gather quantitative and qualitative impact data.

Dedicated **social media campaigns** were designed and launched on occasion of engagement initiatives involving the civil society at EU and international level, including:

- October 2022: social media campaign raising awareness on the clustering initiative with ZeroWaste, FRONTSH1P, SISTERS, ENOUGH, ClieNFarms project in the context of the Circular Week 2022;
- February 2023: social media campaign “#DearLittleScientist” carried out in the context of the International Day of Women and Girls in science.

For the above campaigns, dedicated visuals and videos (<https://twitter.com/Agro2Circular/status/1623301871392931841/video/1>) have been developed.

Figure 11 Social media card and video

Table 8 Social media campaigns

Social media campaign	Social media	Timing
#CircularWeek2022	Twitter/LinkedIn	October 2022
#DearLittleScientist	Twitter/LinkedIn	February 2023

Table 9 Social media main info

Accountability	ICONS is responsible for the core social media activities: setting up the accounts, posting, following existing social media channels and monitoring outreach. The consortium partners are encouraged to contribute by joining the community of Agro2Circular Twitter and LinkedIn followers. They can retweet and repost our content from their organisations' channels and use the #Agro2Circular.
Input	ICONS distributes original project news and events on Agro2Circular social media channels, retweets and reposts events and news that are interesting for the project's community and help increase visibility and engagement of Agro2Circular partner's posts and tweets. ICONS also designed original social media campaigns on Agro2Circular-related topics. PRIMAFRIO as local outreach leaders, and KVC as engagement leader, are in charge of updating the Spanish website with news and events. All partners contribute by posting their original content about the project or engaging with Agro2Circular social media account activities.
Timing/ deviation	Ongoing Agro2Circular Twitter and LinkedIn accounts active since the start of the project
Task/deliverable	Task 8.2
Link	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/agro2circular/?viewAsMember=true Twitter: https://twitter.com/Agro2Circular

Multipliers

Agro2Circular aims to maximise the impact of its editorial production through an *ad hoc* distribution strategy, exploiting several online multipliers.

The public communication tools for media distribution are:

- information multipliers (e.g., AlphaGalileo, Phys.org, youris.com)
- press and dedicated online portals (e.g., BiorefineCluster)

Table 10 Media multipliers main info

Accountability	ICONS is responsible for distributing the news and press releases and journalistic articles to external news multipliers. The consortium partners are encouraged to re-distribute these materials within their networks. Monitoring will measure the outreach of Agro2Circular communication materials.
Input	All project partners contribute with statements, news items to be promoted and help with the distribution, advertising the news and press releases on their social media channels/ newsletters/ websites etc
Timing/ deviation	ongoing
Task/ deliverable	Task 8.4
Link	AlphaGalileo: https://www.alphagalileo.org/en-gb/ Phys.org: https://phys.org/ Youris.com: https://www.youris.com/ BiorefineCluster Europe: https://www.biorefine.eu

4. Communication and engagement at local and regional level

Lectures/workshops at regional schools, Universities and educative events to raise awareness on A2C topics

In line with D8.1, tailor-made events to attract the general public have been carried out by Agrofood, through conferences and workshops addressed to both the local public and the regional industry sector, facilitating the circular economy approach. These include:

- Conference on Wastewater Treatment and Regeneration. R+D+d+I lines (27 April 2022) C/Concordia, s/n, 30500 Molina de Segura.
- CEEIC-INFO (17 May 2022), online. Dissemination of results of projects funded by public calls for proposals in the area of Food Technology.
- PIDDE Programme - CTNC, Ministry of Science and Innovation and Seneca Foundation of the Region of Murcia (24 May 2022), Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena. News from the agri-food sector.
- Programa PIDDE – CTNC (3 June 2022), Universidad de Murcia Veterinaria.
- Semana de la Ciencia (21-23 October 2022), participation in the Science and Technology Week of the Region of Murcia organised by the Seneca Foundation, promoting the forthcoming launch of the Circular Game (Primafrio).

The following images are referred to the above-mentioned dissemination actions.

Figure 12 Local C&D activities

Worth highlighting the next dissemination opportunity at local level, being, the Biowaste Club (26 April 2023), Murcia. Challenges for industry to implement the circular bioeconomy.

On the other hand, training has begun in secondary schools, secondary schools and vocational training centres with talks on the following contents:

TALLERES

Bienvenidos al maravilloso mundo de la economía circular, un concepto cada vez más importante para la sostenibilidad del planeta.

Los talleres sobre economía circular están diseñados para proporcionar a los estudiantes de institutos, ciclos formativos y otros centros de enseñanza una comprensión profunda de los beneficios y la necesidad de la economía circular.

Nuestros talleres están diseñados para ser interactivos y educativos. Los estudiantes tendrán la oportunidad de trabajar en equipo y desarrollar habilidades valiosas.

No pierdas la oportunidad de participar en nuestros talleres sobre economía circular.

¡Aprende cómo puedes contribuir a la sostenibilidad del planeta y ser parte del cambio hacia un futuro más sostenible!

CONTENIDOS

TALLER "ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR"

Cursos recomendados: 1º-4ºESO y 1º de BACH

Contenidos:

1. Economía lineal vs Economía circular
2. ¿Qué es la economía circular?
3. ¿Qué se hace en Europa? El Plan de Acción de Economía Circular y el proyecto Agro2circular
4. Y yo... ¿Qué puedo hacer?

TALLER "BIOTECNOLOGÍA Y BIOPLÁSTICOS EN LA ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR"

Cursos recomendados: 1º-2º de BACH y otros ciclos formativos.

Contenidos:

1. ¿Qué es la biotecnología?
2. Aplicaciones de la biotecnología
3. Bioplásticos
4. Biotecnología como herramienta
5. ¿Qué hacemos en CETEC BIOTECHNOLOGY? Agro2circular.
6. Residuos de la industria agroalimentaria.

TALLER "RECICLADO DE PLÁSTICOS"

Cursos recomendados: 1º-2º de BACH y otros ciclos formativos.

Contenidos:

1. ¿Dónde reciclar?
2. Legislación y objetivos
3. Envases de plástico
4. Tipos de plásticos
5. Tipos de separación de residuos plásticos
6. Proyecto AGRO2CIRCULAR

- Circular Economy" workshops: Interactive workshop explaining the basic concepts of the Circular Economy, and dissemination of the Agro2circular project

- Talk on "Biotechnology and bioplastics in the Circular Economy" (16 February 2023) at the Instituto Poeta Julian Andugar de Santomera, with the attendance of 40 students and two teachers.
- CETEC and PrimaFrio Foundation, gave four talks on "Circular Economy", "Recycling" and "Biotechnology", to more than 150 students.

Given by CETEC, Kveloce and PrimaFrio Foundation, carried out in 2 centres and already committed to ten more talks in six different centres.

Figure 13 A2C Local lectures

This action is also linked to activity 7.1.2 Training Workshops in the street market activity, where twice a month, in the Alhama de Murcia street market, the PrimaFrio Foundation carries out activities to disseminate the project, together with small recycling workshops.

Figure 14 A2C activities at the local market

The local dissemination actions are promoted through the Spanish section of the A2C website: <https://agro2circular.eu/es/>

Regional contests for scholars

This competition activity has been combined with the production of the video game, considering its greater impact by involving the beneficiaries of this action in the creation, themselves, of a video game linked to the circular economy.

This is, with the Circular Game initiative, which Primafrío Foundation is developing within the Agro2circular Project, allows the fulfilment of this goal, providing training in circular economy that will allow a paradigm shift in the way of producing and consuming, making young people aware of and involved in the need for environmental sustainability.

Figure 15 A2C Regional contests

To this end, 52 workshops on circular economy and programming have been developed for more than 400 primary and secondary school students:

<https://arcade.makecode.com/S02526-15943-00154-22617>

The training has been given in 6 educational centres in Alhama de Murcia and Murcia (and districts), resulting in more than 75 teams with their corresponding video game, related to

the circular economy to present them in the final of the Circular Game competition next May with awards and diplomas.

Figure 16 Circular Game

Educating at an early age on the need for environmental sustainability is undoubtedly one of the pillars on which the resolution of the problem must be based, and the use of interactive tools such as video games contributes to bringing different subjects closer to young people, who learn to approach them in a more enjoyable and fun way.

The objective pursued with Circular Game is also to help awaken students' technological vocations, along with transversal skills (creativity, teamwork, problem solving, etc.) and to encourage them to think about and be aware of the importance of the circular economy for their future.

Production of a short documentary film

A dedicated audiovisual production has started with the aim to produce a short documentary showing the global problem of agri-food waste and how the local partners of A2C are providing solutions to solve it as well as to raise awareness on A2C while fostering community engagement on circular economy practices. Following the quadruple helix approach, other entities from different sectors as well as the community's commitment to circular and climate-neutral practices have been involved in this process.

This piece is also serving to provide content for dissemination, through short video pills, in the RRSS to the project with short interviews, currently filmed and scheduled for publication, which began on 6 April 2023.

Figure 17 Short interviews

Table 11 Local Communication and Engagement activities main info

Accountability	PRIMAFRIO is responsible for the overall execution of Communication and engagement at Local and regional level, with support from PROEX, AGRO, KVC, CARM, CJM, INFO. ICONS is involved by supporting the promotion through A2C channels and design of dedicated communication products.
Input	
Timing/ deviation	ongoing
Task/ deliverable	Task 8.3
Link	A2C website (ES section): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homepage: https://agro2circular.eu/es/ • News&Events: https://agro2circular.eu/es/noticias-y-eventos/

5.Events and clustering activities

Agro2Circular, through the consortium partners, is taking part in several conferences, workshops and dissemination activities. The aim of taking part in these events is to expand the collaboration network, raise awareness on the project, sharing progress and gathering feedbacks from other experts.

Events

Agro2Circular partners disseminated the project and its results at the following events:

Table 12 Summary of events attended

Partner ShortName	Partner's role (Organiser, Speaker, Attendee, Other)	WORKSHOP	Title of the event	Date (DD/MM/YYYY)	Place	Target										Size of Audience (N. of attendees)	Countries addressed (national, EU, international)	URL	Language(s)	
						Scientific Community	Industry	Civil Society	General Public	Policy makers	Investors	Customers	Media	Other	Total audience					
WETSUS	Attendee	EXHIBITION	Aquatech Amsterdam, world's leading water trade show for process, drinking and wastewater	2/11/2021	Amsterdam, Netherlands	x	x									15000		International	https://www.aquatechtrade.com/amsterdam/	
CTNC	Speaker	OTHER	II Day of meetings with iWATERMAP project partners	04/11/21	Murcia, Spain	x	x			x						15		EU		
CETBIO	Speaker	TRADE FAIR	INNOVAM ±	09/11/21	Cartagena, Spain	x	45			x						270		National	INNOVAM+Website	English
AGROFOOD/CTNC	Attendee	TRADE FAIR	INNOVAM ±	09/11/21	Cartagena, Spain														INNOVAM+Website	Spanish
INFO	Other	OTHER				x	45			x						270		National		

CTNC	Speaker			03/02/22		x	x			x					10		International	https://ctnc.es/noticias-ctnc/el-ctnc-recibe-a-la-delegacion-de-expertos-de-azerbaiyan-en-el-marco-del-proyecto-europeo-europead-improved-support-to-entreprenurial-development-in-rural-areas-of-azerbaijan/	English
CETBIO	Speaker	WORKSHOP	Bio-Based Plastics Webinar	01/02/22	Online	x	x									105	International	https://youtu.be/j3qUGZfFCjU	
CETEC	Other	OTHER	Broadcast 7TV Región de Murcia	05/02/22	Murcia			x	x				923000		923000		National	LINK	
AGROFOOD	Other	OTHER	Company meeting - Citrus	24/02/22	Murcia		x							1	1		National		Spanish
AGROFOOD	Other	OTHER	Company meeting - Broccoli	17/02/22	Murcia		x							1	1		National		Spanish
CTNC	Speaker	OTHER	Dissemination of the	16/02/22	University				x						30		National		Spanish

			project in the Food Science and Technology degree course on innovation strategies		of Murcia													
CETEC	Other	OTHER	Broadcast Cadena Ser Radio	01/03/22	Murcia			x					21000		21000	National		
EURADA	Speaker	CONFERENCE	I Congreso de Etiquetado Inteligente	17/03/22	Jabugo	x	x			x					50	National	https://congresoetiquetadointeligente.eu/	Spanish
CETEC	Speaker	WORKSHOP	Circular Plastics Alliance - General Assembly R&D Side Session	24/03/22	Online	x	x			x					50	EU	Link	English
GWC/CETEC	Speaker	CONFERENCE	Agricultural film conference	29-30/03/22	Barcelona	x	x							96		International	Link	English
CETEC/CTNC	Attendee	CONFERENCE	MeetingPack2022	20-21/04/22	Valencia		x							14		International	link	Spanish/English
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	JORNADA TRATAMIENTO Y REGENERACIÓN DE AGUAS RESIDUALES. LÍNEAS DE I+D+i	27/04/22	Molina de Segura-Murcia	x	x			x				30		EU	Link	Spanish

CETEC/EURADA/ICONS	Speaker	WORKSHOP	LOOP-Cluster Launch Workshop	24/05/22	Genoa	x	x	x		x						100	EU		English
SOLPLAST	Other	WORKSHOP	CCRI FOCUS GROUP	05/05/22	ONLINE			X								6	EU		English
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	CRECESTARUP Agrifoodtech	17/05/22	online		x			x						15	National		Spanish
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	JORNADA I+D+i AGROALIMENTARIA	24/05/22	Cartagena-Murcia	x	x		x	x						20	National		Spanish
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	JORNADA DESCUBRIMIENTO EMPRENDEDOR. Sector Agroalimentario	27/05/22	Molina de Segura-Murcia	x				x						40	National		Spanish
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	NOVEDADES EN EL SECTOR AGROALIMENTARIO	03/06/22	Murcia	x	x		x	x						30	National		Spanish
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	Jornada Fomento de la Innovación en el Sector Agroalimentario 2022	29/06/22	Murcia	x	x		x	x						30	National		Spanish
AGROFOOD	Speaker	Workshop	Food for Life	14/06/22	Madrid												National	Food for Life GT calidad.	Spanish

																		producción y sostenibilidad		
CTNC	Other	TRADE FAIR	NUTRACEUTICALS EUROPE	16-17/06/22	Barcelona	x	x											International	https://www.nutraceuticalseurope.com/en/event/	English
AGROFOOD	Other	OTHER	Company meeting - Artichoke	04/07/22	Murcia		x							1	1			National		Spanish
AGROFOOD/CTNC	Attendee	WORKSHOP	Food for Life Spain https://foodforlife-spain.es/gt-sector-hortofruticola/	05/07/22	Almería-online	x	x							25				National	Food for Life GT Hortofruticola https://foodforlife-spain.es/gt-sector-hortofruticola/	Spanish
AGROFOOD/CTNC	Attendee	WORKSHOP	Workshop PestNuts sister projects	07/07/22	online	x	x											International		English
CTNC/AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	III Congreso Universitario en Innovación y Sostenibilidad Agroalimentaria (CUISA)	15-16/09/22	UMH Orihuela	x	x		x									National		Spanish
EURADA/ICONS	Organiser	OTHER	Circular Week 2022 - Making the Agri-Food Sector Circular	06/10/22	online	x	x			x						102		EU	https://circularweek.org/en/online/making-the-agri-food-	English

																		sector-circular/		
CTNC/CETEC/AGROFOOD	Other	EXHIBITION	Semana de la Ciencia y la Tecnología	21-23/10/2022	Murcia	x		x	x									National	https://semanadelaciencia.csic.es/	Spanish
CETEC	Attendee	TRADE FAIR	K2022	24-26/10/2022	Düsseldorf - Germany		x							21	21		International	K2022	English	
CETEC	Speaker	CONFERENCE	BIOPOL2022	14-16 November 2022	University of Alicante - Spain	x									140		International		English	
CTNC	Speaker	OTHER	Valorización de residuos agrícolas para la creación de nuevos materiales técnicos sostenibles	01/12/22	Online	x	x								30		National		Spanish	
CETEC	Speaker	OTHER	Networking event Research institutes Region of Murcia	21/12/22	CTNC_Murcia	x									30		National	Link	Spanish	
EVERY	Speaker	EXHIBITION	AIPIA (Active & Intelligent Packaging Industry Association)	14/11/2022-15/11/2022	Amsterdam	x	x							500	500		International	Link	English	

			n) World Congress 2022																	
DMC	Speaker	CONFERENCE	Bioeconomía Circular en el sector oleícola	29/08/2022-30/08/2022	Universidad Internacional de Andalucía (UNIA), Baeza, Jaén	x		x										National	https://www.unia.es/es/noticias/la-unia-analiza-en-un-curso-de-verano-de-la-sede-antonio-machado-de-baeza-la-bioeconomia-circular-en-el-sector-oleicola	Spanish
DMC	Other	OTHER	European Research Night: Obtaining active principles from by-products of the agri-food industry for the control of emerging pathogens	30/09/22	Online	x			x					133	133			International	https://lanchedelosinvestigadores.fundaciondescubre.es/actividades/obtencion-de-principios-activos-a-partir-de-subproductos-de-la-industria-agroalimentaria-para-el-control-de-	English

																		patogenos-emergentes/	
CETEC	Speaker	WORKSHOP	Innovative R&D projects in Circular Economy-Curso de Tecnico especialista Gestor de Economía Circular	19/01/23	Online		x							12	12	National			Spanish
CETECBIO	Speaker	Workshop	Biotechnology in Circular Economy at Secondary School (IES Poeta Julian Andugar)	16/02/23	Face to Face			x	x				Students	42	42	Regional			Spanish
KVC	Speaker	WORKSHOP	Circular Economy presentation at Secondary School (IES Ruiz de Alda)	24/02/23	Presential (San Javier, Murcia)			x	x				Students	80	80	Regional			Spanish
Almond	Other	TRADE FAIR	BIOFACH	14-17 Feb 2023	Nürnberg, Germany		x							40	40	International	https://www.biofach.de/en/news/press-releases/2023-biofach-closing-report	English	

																		o8jwq34ks s_pireport		
SAPERATE C	Other	TRA DE FAIR	K 2022	19/10/ 22- 26/10/ 22	Düss eldorf - Germ any		x				x	x					177486	Internation al	https://ww w.k- online.co m/	German, English
CETBIO	Spea ker	CON FERE NCE	I Jornada de biotecnolo gía: innovación e impacto en nuestra región (1st Biotechnol ogy journey: innovation and impact in the Region of Murcia)	sette mbre 2022	Murci a, Spain			x	x		x		x					Regional	https://ww w.laopinio ndemurcia .es/evento s/biotecno logia/	Spanish
CETBIO	Other	WOR KSH OP	Internation al Workshop on Sustainabl e Chemistry	01/05/ 23	Carta gena, Spain	x												Internation al	https://ww w.iwsusch em2023.o rg/	English
PRIMA/KVC /CETEC/EV ERSIA	Orga niser	EXHI BITIO N	launch of community based activity in Alhama de Murcia	22/01/ 22	Alha ma de Murci a, Spain			x	x	x								Regional		Spanish
Wetsus	Atten dee	WOR KSH OP	Meeting with the Dutch Water Authorities		Onlin e	x				x					10			National	Energie en Grondstoff en Fabriek (efgf.nl)	English
Wetsus																				

CJM	Speaker	OTHER	Webinar "Bioeconomía circular en los subproductos hortofrutícolas"	09/03/23	Online	x			x						150	79	National		Spanish
EVERSIA	Other	WORKSHOP	CCRI FOCUS GROUP	05/05/22	Online			X								6	EU		English
AGROFOOD	Attendee	BROKERAGE EVENT	IKNOWLEDGE FORUM - Brokerage Event	04/10/2022-05/10/2022	Cartagena - Murcia, Spain	x				x				x			International	https://i-knowledgeforum.com/	English
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	Innovación agroalimentaria. Tendencias y oportunidades	11/10/22	UMU - Facultad Biología, Spain	x			x							44	National	https://www.ctnc.eu/cursos/jornada-innovacion-agroalimentaria-tendencias-y-oportunidades-programa-pidde-11-de-octubre/	Spanish
AGROFOOD	Attendee	TRADE FAIR	Innovam+22	25/10/22	Innovam+2022	x	x	x	x								International	https://www.innovamrm.com/	Spanish
AGROFOOD	Attendee	OTHER	ALIBETOPIAS 2022. New technological	27/10/22	Alibetopías	x	x										National	https://www.alibetopias.es/	Spanish

			environme nts																
AGROFOOD	Speaker	EXHIBITION	Weekly market diffusion	13/12/22	Alhama de Murcia, Spain			x	x									National	Spanish
AGROFOOD	Speaker	WORKSHOP	Escuela de Verano del proyecto ERASMUS SEDDS	20/9/22	Molina de Segura, Spain	x			x						10		International	English	
AGROFOOD	Speaker	CONFERENCE	El valor oculto de los subproductos agroalimentarios - Estrategias de Economía Circular	1/3/23	Online - UAH Madrid	x			x						10		National	Spanish	
SOLPLAST	Attendee	OTHER	CEN TC 249/WG7. Necesidad de modificar las Normativas de filmes agrícolas para incluir el uso de productos reciclados en estos materiales	21/03/22	ONLINE									X	9		EU	English	
SOLPLAST	Attendee	OTHER	CEN TC 249/WG 11. Se	08/09/22	ONLINE									X			EU	English	

			revisan todas las Normas relativas al reciclado, mostrando trabajos de los comités nacionales , y posibles acuerdos con otras entidades de normalización															
SOLPLAST	Attendee	OTHER	CEN TC 249/WG 11. Se revisan todas las Normas relativas al reciclado, mostrando trabajos de los comités nacionales , y posibles acuerdos con otras entidades de normalización	30/11/22	ONLINE								X				EU	English

EURADA	Attendee	CONFERENCE	2023 European Circular Economy Stakeholder Conference	27/02/23-28/02/23	Brussels	x	x	x	x	x	x		x		~1000	~1000	EU	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/annual-conference-2023-recovery-open-strategic-autonomy-and-resilience	English
PROEXPO RT	Organiser	CONFERENCE	PROEXPORT GENERAL ASSEMBLY	23/09/22	Aguilas, Murcia, Spain		x	x	x	x	x		x		250	250	National	Asociación - Proexport	Spanish
PROEXPO RT	Attendee	TRADE FAIR	FRUITATTENTION-2022	04/10/22	Madrid, Spain		x	x	x	x		x	x		180	90000	International	https://www.ifema.es/en/fruit-attraction	English/Spanish
PROEXPO RT	Attendee	EXHIBITION	SEMANA DE LA CIENCIA (Week of the Science)	21/10/22	Murcia, Spain			x	x				x		60	4500	National	Semana de la Ciencia Murcia 2022: consulta la programación en el Malecón de Murcia (laopiniondemurcia.es)	Spanish
PROEXPO RT	Attendee	TRADE FAIR	FRUITLOGISTICA-2023	09/02/23	Berlin, Deutschland		x	x	x	x	x	x	x		150	40000	International	FRUIT LOGISTICA - 8-10 Febrero 2023	Spanish

GWC	Speaker	CONFERENCE	Agricultural film Europe	6-8 March 2023	Barcelona, Spain		x							75	75	International	AMI Agricultural Film	English
CETEC	Speaker	H2020 EVENT	Innovation Forum 4 Plastics	14-15 March 2023	Brussels	x	x			x				65	65	International	Innovation Forum 4 Plastics	English
CTNC	Speaker	CONFERENCE	Industrialización. Nuevas oportunidades para el sector agrícola de Cieza	23/03/23	Cieza		x	x	x				x	70	70	National	https://cadenaaser.com/murcia/2023/03/23/cieza-acoge-agrojornada-en-floracion-ser-arconorte/	Spanish

Table 13 Events main info

Accountability	ICONS is responsible for keeping track of all the events in which any one of the Agro2Circular partners will participate. All the partners are to organise in-house events – workshops, trainings, webinars – to showcase Agro2Circular outcomes and raise awareness among a professional audience.
Timing/ deviation	<i>Upcoming</i>
Task/ deliverable	Task 8.5
Link	https://Agro2Circularproject.eu/events/

Below, some pictures of the most relevant A2C communication and dissemination activities are displayed:

Oral presentation by CETECBIO in the regional event “INNOVAM” attended by 270 representatives from the industrial sector, public sector and scientific community

TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR

- A2C will valorise fruits & vegetables wastes by green routes to obtain bioactives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods, and cosmetics.
- A2C will develop the first recycling value chain for post-industrial multilayer films based on a synergistic approach combining innovative sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerization, decontamination & mechanical recycling.
- A2C will implement a Data Integration System (DIS) as a digital tool for ensuring traceability and as Predictive Decision Tool in the agrifood sector.
- This systemic solution and circular economy approach will be tested in the Region of Murcia (Spain) and replicated in other two other EU countries (Italy and Lithuania).

<https://agro2circular.eu>

Oral presentation by CETECBIO in the international Bio-Based Plastics Webinar attended by 105 industrial and scientific organisations (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j3qUGZfFCjU>)

Oral presentation by GWC in the [International Agricultural Film Conference](#) with an audience of 96 representatives mainly from the industrial sector

Oral presentation by CETEC in [Biopol international Conference](#) to 140 attendees from the scientific community

Poster presented by Wetsus in Aquatech exhibition

Science Week – Murcia Spain- 14,000 m² and 87 stands open to general public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

Presentation of A2C in Everything exhibitor booth in AIPIA World Congress (more than 500 participants and around 20 exhibitors)

Presentation of Agro2Circular in the [European Researchers Night](#) by DMC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

— **Paco Sánchez** [Radio Murcia](#) 01/03/2022 - 18:18 h CET

Radio broadcast by CETEC (<https://cadenaser.com/2022/03/01/europa-en-la-antena-de-la-ser-se-interesa-por-el-proyecto-agro2circular/>) with a audience of 2 1000 citizens

● Informativos

Bioplásticos 'made in' Alhama de Murcia para sustituir a los derivados del petróleo

CM 07/02/2022 12:03

0 0 0 0 comentarios

En el Centro Tecnológico del Calzado y el Plástico de Alhama buscan materiales que puedan sustituir a los derivados del petróleo. A día de hoy coordinan dos proyectos europeos que buscan materiales que sean más respetuosos con el medio ambiente. Uno de ellos también podría ayudar a descontaminar el acuífero del Campo de Cartagena y frenar parte de la entrada de nitratos al Mar Menor.

CETEC es coordinador de los proyectos Europeos upPET y Agro2Circular, donde se está desarrollando el proceso de producción de plástico biodegradable, entre otras actividades, con una financiación de cerca de 25 millones de euros. El agua del acuífero del Campo de Cartagena está contaminada, y si se extrae y se trata para poder usarla en riego genera residuos de salmuera. En este laboratorio han encontrado una posible solución, un proceso que se inicia aquí, donde ponen ese residuo en contacto con bacterias para su cultivo.

Presentation of A2C by CETEC, Regional television broadcast news with an audience of 923.000 citizens (<http://7tvregiondemurcia.es/bioplasticos-para-sustituir-a-los-derivados-del-petroleo-made-in-alhama-de-murcia/>)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

Aplicación de tecnologías innovadoras para la obtención de productos con valor añadido a partir de subproductos de alcachofa

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INTRODUCCIÓN Y OBJETIVO

Las Frutas y Verduras (F y V) son el grupo que mayor contribución de residuos alimentarios aporta a la cadena de suministro alimentaria, con más del 40%. Estos residuos alimentarios son una excelente fuente de compuestos bioactivos naturales. Sin embargo, estos residuos de F y V no están siendo explotados por el sector. El proyecto titulado "Territorial Circular Systemic solution for the Upcycling of Residues from the Agrifood Sector", conocido como Agro2Circular, tiene entre sus objetivos valorizar estos residuos a través de rutas verdes (innovadoras) para obtener compuestos bioactivos para la producción de nutracéuticos, alimentos funcionales, entre otros productos. El caso concreto de la alcachofa ha sido evaluado teniendo en cuenta que estudios realizados por diversos autores (Frattinini y col., 2007; Coim y col., 2006), señalan que las hojas externas de alcachofa de algunas variedades poseen concentraciones importantes de compuestos fenólicos con actividad antioxidante. El objetivo de este trabajo es dar a conocer directamente al sector agroalimentario los beneficios del uso de tecnologías innovadoras, como la extracción asistida con ultrasonidos y la extracción enzimática frente a la extracción acuosa convencional, así como procesos de purificación con resinas y estabilización mediante liofilización, para la obtención de extractos con capacidad antioxidante a partir de restos de alcachofa.

METODOLOGÍA

EXTRACCIÓN ACUOSA 1:3 p/v 1 hora 98 °C	EXTRACCIÓN ENZIMÁTICA 1:3 p/v VALIDASE® TRL (0.01% de matriz) 1 hora 25 °C	EXTRACCIÓN ASISTIDA CON ULTRASONIDOS 1:3 p/v 90 % amplitud (164 W) 1 hora 75 °C
--	--	--

Purificación - Resina PAD900

ADSORCIÓN - DESORCIÓN (x2)

1:10 p/v
3 horas
25 °C

1:3 p/v
EtOH 50%
1 hora
45 °C

ESTABILIZACIÓN - Liofilizador
48 horas

RESULTADOS Y CONCLUSIONES

Subproducto alcachofa	Extracto 1. Extracción acuosa	Extracto 2. Extracción enzimática	Extracto 3. Extracción asistida con ultrasonidos
ABTS (mg/kg Trolox/g muestra)	41,35	92,84	118,68
Rendimiento (%)	3,02	1,23	2,92

CAPACIDAD ANTIOXIDANTE MEDIANTE MÉTODO ABTS (IN VITRO)

+ ABTS⁺
10 µL 1000 µL

Medida absorbancia a 734 nm
CURVA TROLOX

4 min

CAPACIDAD ANTIOXIDANTE MEDIANTE LA TÉCNICA DE IMPEDANCIA (IN VIVO)

Rendimiento: gramos extracto obtenido a partir de 100 g de peso fresco de subproducto.

Este proyecto ha recibido financiación del programa de investigación e innovación Horizonte 2020 de la Unión Europea (convocatoria Green Deal) en virtud de un acuerdo de subvención No 101036838 (Oct 2021-Sep 2024). Más información <https://agro2circular.eu/>

III Congreso Universitario en Innovación y Sostenibilidad Agroalimentaria (CUISA)

15 y 16 de septiembre de 2022

Poster by CTNC in the "III Congreso Universitario en Innovación y Sostenibilidad Agroalimentaria (CUISA)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

Clustering activities

Clustering activities, close cooperation and joint dissemination strategies and campaigns with other EU like-minded projects tackling the same topics are implemented to foster knowledge transfer and to increase impact and engagement among wider audiences with Agro2Circular project.

After an initial inventory and mapping of networking and clustering opportunities at European level, the Agro2Circular project started to reach out to other projects and initiatives in M5 (February 2022).

The following table provides an overview of the networking and clustering activities carried out so far.

Table 14 Clustering and networking activities

Cluster/ initiative	Type	Lead Partner	A2C Involved Partners	Description	Date	Name	A2C Partner Attended	Info & Documents
LOOP	Projects Cooperation	EURADA	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS	Collaboration cluster between the four sister projects of the GD3.2 Call (EcoeFISHent, CIRCULAR FOAM, FRONTSH1P & Agro2Circular)	24.05. 2022	GD3.2 LOOP Workshop on how to build a low-carbon, climate resilient future for cities and regions	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS	Launch workshop of the cluster, including presentations of the four projects as well as inputs from high-level speakers on how to build a low-carbon, climate resilient future for cities and regions. Link to recording
LOOP	Projects Cooperation	EURADA	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS	Collaboration cluster between the four sister projects of the GD3.2 Call (EcoeFISHent, CIRCULAR FOAM, FRONTSH1P & Agro2Circular)	12.07. 2022	LOOP-Cluster Coordination Meeting		
LOOP	Projects Cooperation	EURADA	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS	Collaboration cluster between the four sister projects of the GD3.2 Call (EcoeFISHent, CIRCULAR FOAM, FRONTSH1P & Agro2Circular)	02.12. 2022	Alignment meeting between CCRI-CSO & LOOP	EURADA	

LOOP	Projects Cooperation	EURADA	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS	Collaboration cluster between the four sister projects of the GD3.2 Call (EcoeFISHent, CIRCULAR FOAM, FRONTSH1P & Agro2Circular)	05.12.2022	LOOP Follow-up meeting	EURADA, CETEC	Meeting of the four LOOP projects to discuss future course of the initiative
LOOP	Projects Cooperation	EURADA	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS	Collaboration cluster between the four sister projects of the GD3.2 Call (EcoeFISHent, CIRCULAR FOAM, FRONTSH1P & Agro2Circular)	03.02.2023	Meeting between CCRI & LOOP	EURADA	Meeting between the CCRI (EC & Ecorys) and the LOOP initiative to discuss collaboration opportunities and to avoid overlaps
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys	CETEC, EURADA, KVELOCE, Eversia, SOLPLAST	The CCRI initiative is part of the New Circular Economy Action Plan, and it aims at supporting the implementation of circular systemic solutions at local and regional level by providing assistance to cities and regions.	29.06.2022	Coordination meeting to discuss a questionnaire and future cooperation with the CCRI-CSO	CETEC, EURADA	<u>Meeting with Jan Wynarski on cooperation between Agro2Circular and CCRI. Agreement to work on the questionnaire continuously throughout the project.</u> Link to questionnaire
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.	05.05.2022	Focus Group with Industrial and Business Stakeholders	CETEC, Eversia, SOLPLAST	Link to recording Link to presentation
Circular Cities	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial	29.10.2022	1st CCRI Webinar:	EURADA	

and Regions Initiative (CCRI)				stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.		Presentation on the CCRI Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale		
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.	15.12.2022	2nd CCRI Webinar - New Horizon Europe calls for proposals for circular economy at local and regional scale	EURADA	
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.	07.02.2023	3rd CCRI Webinar - Monitoring the Transition to Circular Economy	EURADA	
Circular Cities	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial	27.02.2023	CCRI TWG Bioeconomy -	EURADA, KVC, UB	

and Regions Initiative (CCRI)				stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.		pre-meeting with CCRI Projects		
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.	07.03.2023	TWG Industrial Symbiosis - first meeting	EURADA, KVC, UB	
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.	08.03.2023	TWG Bioeconomy - first meeting	EURADA	
Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)	EC Initiative	Ecorys		Focus Group to gather feedback from industrial stakeholders on the creation of a knowledge observatory to be hosted on the CCRI website.	16.03.2023	CCRI & GD-SO working groups coordination meeting	EURADA	Meeting to discuss the involvement of the GD3.2 projects in the working groups of the CCRI and GD-SO
Green Deal Working Group:	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call	02.&03.03.2022	Information Session - Presentation, FAQ and		Link to presentation Link to Q&A Link to GDC projects database

Food Cluster				and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.		Projects Database		
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	31.05.2022	GD-SO Food Working Group kick-off meeting		Link to minutes
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	22.06.2022	Board of Coordinators meeting	CETEC	
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	06.10.2022	Webinar as part of the Circular Week 2022	CETEC, EURADA, ICONS, Kveloce	Link to recording
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	24.10.2022	GDSO Webinar - Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change	EURADA	

Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	15.11.2022	GD-SO Food Working Group 2nd meeting	EURADA	
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	12.01.2023	Non-public workshop	CETEC, EURADA, KVC, UVEG	Dialogue on selected European Green Deal Policy Priorities
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	22.02.2023	GD-SO Food WG Action 2.1	EURADA, KVC	Meeting to discuss the mapping of stakeholders and database
Green Deal Working Group: Food Cluster	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects Support Office		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.	23.02.2023	GD-SO Food WG Action 2.1	CETEC, EURADA, KVC	Meeting to discuss the mapping of common drivers & barriers
Green Deal	EC Initiative	Green Deal Projects		Mission of the GD-SO is to facilitate coordination between	16.03.2023	CCRI & GD-SO working groups	EURADA	Meeting to discuss the involvement of the GD3.2

Working Group: Food Cluster		Support Office		projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal Call and maximise their positive impact in the longer term.		coordination meeting		projects in the working groups of the CCRI and GD-SO
EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub	EC Initiative	European Commission Initiative	ICONS, EURADA	Open contact point on food loss and waste prevention. Includes a database of good practices, a Member States portal providing information on national policies and legislative developments, and a news section.	20.10.2022	13th meeting of the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste		Link to project page
European Circular Plastics Alliance	EC Initiative		CETEC, EURADA	Open to all public and private actors from European plastics value chains that are ready to actively contribute to delivering on the declaration of the alliance. There are currently 311 signatories.	22.02.2022	European Circular Plastics Alliance General Assembly	CETEC, EURADA	
Biorefinery Cluster Europe	Projects Cooperation	Ghent University	EURADA, ICONS	The Biorefinery Cluster Europe interconnects projects and people within the domain of biobased resource recovery, striving to contribute to a more sustainable resource management.	23.08.2022	Introductory Call	CETEC, EURADA	Link to project page

FOODR US Cooperation and Collaboration Network (tbc)	Projects Cooperation	FOODRUS Project University of Deusto	tbc					
PestNu Clusteri n Activitie s	Projects Cooperation	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	CTNC, Agrofood	Collaboration cluster between the different sister projects of the PestNu (Agro2Circular, WASTE4GREEN, EcoeFISHent, ZeroW, SISTERS, ClieNfarms & NeoGiant) project through round tables to assess opportunities and synergies (RT3: Food Wastes)	08.07. 2022	1st WORKSHOP ON CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES OF PESTNU'S SISTER PROJECTS	CTNC, Agrofood	
PREVE NT Waste Alliance	Multi- Stakeholder Alliance/Platf orm	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationa le Zusammen arbeit	CETEC	The Prevent Waste Alliance serves as a platform for exchange and international cooperation. Organisations from the private sector, academia, civil society and public institutions jointly engage for a circular economy.	17.11. 2022	General Assembly	CETEC	Link to information of the event

		(Secretariat)						
PREVENT Waste Alliance	Multi-Stakeholder Alliance/Platform	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (Secretariat)	CETEC	The Prevent Waste Alliance serves as a platform for exchange and international cooperation. Organisations from the private sector, academia, civil society and public institutions jointly engage for a circular economy.	19.12.2022	Plastic working group meeting	CETEC	Minutes
PREVENT Waste Alliance	Multi-Stakeholder Alliance/Platform	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (Secretariat)	CETEC	The Prevent Waste Alliance serves as a platform for exchange and international cooperation. Organisations from the private sector, academia, civil society and public institutions jointly engage for a circular economy.	23.02.2023	PREVENT Matchmaking Workshop with the circular design programme CIRCO on “A proven circular design method to fuel the circular transition”	CETEC	
PREVENT	Multi-Stakeholder	Deutsche Gesellschaft für	CETEC	The Prevent Waste Alliance serves as a platform for exchange and international	28.02.2023	Matchmaking session on “Plastic trade	CETEC	

Waste Alliance	Alliance/Platform	International Zusammenarbeit (Secretariat)		cooperation. Organisations from the private sector, academia, civil society and public institutions jointly engage for a circular economy.		with low and middle income countries”		
HOOP	European Project	CETENMA (Murcia Energy and Environment Technology Centre)	KVC, PRIMAFRIO, AGROFOOD, CETEC	The HOOP project supports 8 lighthouse cities and regions in developing large-scale urban circular bioeconomy initiatives that will focus on making bio-based products from urban biowaste and wastewater.	13.01.2023	Meeting to coordinate potential actions	KVC, AGROFOOD, CETEC	Link to folder
HOOP	European Project	CETENMA (Murcia Energy and Environment Technology Centre)	KVC, PRIMAFRIO, AGROFOOD, CETEC	The HOOP project supports 8 lighthouse cities and regions in developing large-scale urban circular bioeconomy initiatives that will focus on making bio-based products from urban biowaste and wastewater.	26.04.23	Organization of joint event (Biowaste Club) in Murcia with industrial stakeholders of both projects to discuss on challenges to implement CE		
Green Deal Arena	European Project	Shared Green Deal Project	EURADA	European Project initiative	16.09.2022	Introductory Webinar to hybrid 'Green	EURADA	Link to webpage

						Deal Arena' on 4 October 2022.		
Green Deal Arena	European Project	Shared Green Deal Project	EURADA	European Project initiative	04.10.2022	Green Deal Arena' in Brussels.	EURADA	
Green Deal Arena	European Project	Shared Green Deal Project	EURADA	European Project initiative	01.12.2022	2nd Consortium Meeting	CETEC, EURADA	Invitation to other CCRI projects to discuss collaboration (Agro2Circular, FRONTSHIP, HOOP, SUSCHEMIQ)

The first participation in external clustering (Circular Plastics Alliance General Assembly) and networking events (2022 Circular Economy Stakeholder Conference, I Congreso de Etiquetado Inteligente & MeetingPack 2022) was followed by the establishment of a monitoring tool for the different clustering activities carried out by the Agro2Circular project partners. Agro2Circular also had the opportunity to present itself with a booth at the first Festival of the New European Bauhaus during its early stages (dedicated C&D materials were produced – pictures provided below).

Figure 18 A2C at the Festival of the New European Bauhaus 2022

Circularity is the answer

THE COMPASS FOR THE PROVISION OF SUSTAINABLE, TERRITORIAL SYSTEMIC SOLUTIONS

Agro2Circular, an EU project developing a systemic solution for the territorial deployment of circular economy. This circular approach will be shaped around a multidimensional model enabling adoption and scalability of territorial systemic solutions while being sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, fair, boosting urban®ional economies, empowering all actors (citizens, industries, decision makers, academia) and fostering circular practices.

Then, in the third quarter of the project, the initiatives to cluster like-minded European projects started. First to name here is the LOOP cluster - a joint initiative of Agro2Circular and its sister projects (CIRCULAR FOAM, EcoeFISHent & FRONTSHIP), which met for the first time in May 2022 for a first joint workshop in Genoa. The LOOP cluster will also organise a partner event during the EU Green Week 2023.

In addition, the two EU-led initiatives of the Green Deal Support Office (DG-SO) and the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO) started contacting their respective target projects at this time.

While the CCRI's Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) only started their work in March 2023 (Agro2Circular is participating in the TWGs on Bioeconomy and Industrial Symbiosis at the time of writing this report) and the first concrete actions are slowly taking shape, the GD-SO's Food Working Group, which started its activities earlier, has (as of April 2023) begun its activities and created a mapping of stakeholders including a corresponding database and

a mapping of common drivers & barriers so far (with contributions of KVC in shaping the database and including stakeholders)..

The latter GD-SO Food WG also served as the basis for the Agro2Circular-led organisation of a joint webinar of Green Deal projects in the framework of the Circular Week in October 2022.

Further networking and clustering activities included:

- The inclusion of Agro2Circular in the Biorefine Cluster Europe;
- The participation in workshops led by the two GD projects PestNu and SISTERS;
- The portrayal of Agro2Circular on the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub;
- The active participation in the Green Deal Arena (a previous seminar in September 2022; the main event in October 2022, a follow-up seminar in December 2022);
- The participation in the 13th meeting of the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste;
- The participation in the PREVENT Waste Alliance General Assembly;
- The participation in the TREASoURcE Consortium Meeting, which aimed at closer future collaboration between first and second wave CCRI projects;
- A meeting with the HOOP project to coordinate potential future actions. On this regard, the partners KVC, CETEC and AGROFOOD are preparing a joint participatory event (Biowaste Club) on 26th April 2023, in which industrial partners will discuss on the challenges and collaboration opportunities to implement circular economy at the regional level;
- Attendance to the non-public event of GDSO Dialogue on selected European Green Deal Policy Priorities Workshop
- Attendance to CCRI 3rd Webinar - Monitoring the Transition
- to a Circular Economy.
- The attendance of the 2023 Circular Economy Stakeholder Conference;
- And the presentation of Agro2Circular during the Innovation Forum4plastics.

Further networking and clustering activities are planned, with a clear focus on the CCRI and GD-SO working groups.

Launching of the sister projects' cluster Loop in Genoa-Italy

Presentation of A2C by the coordinator in the Circular Plastic Alliance Assembly

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

Meeting with Hoop Project to present A2C and to join the initiative “Biowaste club” and organise future collaboration

Presentation of A2C by the coordinator in the Forum4Plastic March 2023 event in Brussels attended by 65 representatives of H2020 European Projects and REA representatives

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101036838.

Conclusion

Several communication and dissemination activities have been carried out across the M1 – M18 time span. The aim of this deliverable was to give account of what has been produced from the project onset until March 2023, in line with what foreseen in D8.1. The current report will be updated on M34 with D8.3.

